

WHITE GRUB BEETLES ASSOCIATED WITH AGROECOSYSTEM OF PANDHARPUR TEHSIL, DISTRICT SOLAPUR MAHARASHTRA

A. B. MAMLAYYA ¹ | V. R. KAKULTE ² | S. A. VHANALAKAR ³ | ANITA.B. MAMLAYYA ⁴

¹ DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY, KARMAVEER BHAURAO PATIL MAHAVIDYALYA, PANDHARPUR, DIST – SOLAPUR, M.S., INDIA.

² DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY, KTHM COLLEGE, NASHIK, M.S. INDIA.

³ DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY, KARMAVEER HIRE ARTS, SCIENCE, COMMERCE AND EDUCATION COLLEGE, GARGOTI, DIST - KOLHAPUR, M.S. INDIA.

⁴ DR. PATANGRAO KADAM MAHAVIDYALAYA, RAMANADNAGAR BURLI.

ABSTRACT:

The present study reports 15 species of beetles belonging to 9 genera and distributed within four different subfamilies of the family Scarabaeidae viz. Melolonthinae, Rutelinae, Cetoniinae and Dynastinae (Table 1). Subfamily Rutelinae represent 06 species followed by Melolonthinae 05 species, Cetoniinae and Dynastinae 2 species each.

KEYWORDS:

MELOLONTHINAE, RUTELINAE, CETONIINAE, DYNASTINAE, AGROECOSYSTEM, WHITE GRUBS.

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INTRODUCTION

Scarab beetles have been object of research since centuries due to their twofold importance. They are viewed as beneficial as well as harmful insects (Thakare et al., 2011). Several studies have been carried out on the diversity of scarab beetles from the Indian subcontinent (Arrow, 1917, Biswas & Chatterjee, 1985; Chatterjee & Biswas, 2000; Chatterjee, 2004; Sewak, 2006; Ahrens & Fabrizi, 2009; Singh et al., 2010; Li et al., 2010). These studies mostly represent the scarab beetles fauna from the north-eastern states of India. From the review of literature, it appears that there no earlier entomofaunal records from the Pandharpur Tahsil, district Solapur (M.S.) India. To fill up this knowledge gap, the present work has been carried to find out composition of white grub beetles associated with agroecosystem of Pandharpur Tehsil, district Solapur (M.S.) India.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Faunistic surveys of the Pandharpur Tahsil were conducted between May 2019 to November 2021. The beetles were collected from five different localities, viz., Takali, Mendhapur, Sarkoli, Gursale and Ozewadi. The collection and preservation of beetles was followed by the method described by Alfred and Ramakrishna (2004). The identification of the specimens was done by Dr. V.V. Ramamurthy, IARI New Delhi, Insect Identification Service, Dr. Kailsh Chandra, ZSI, Kolkata. The identification of few species was made with the help of available literature

Arrow (1917; 1910).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study reports 15 species of white grub beetles belonging to 9 genera and distributed within four different subfamilies of the family Scarabaeidae viz. Melolonthinae, Rutelinae, Cetoniinae and Dynastinae (Table 1). Subfamily Rutelinae represent 06 species followed by Melolonthinae 05 species, Cetoniinae and Dynastinae 2 species each.

An effort has been made to find out the complex structure of phytophagous scarab beetles from the five different sites of the Pandharpur Tahsil viz. Takali, Gursale, Mendhapur, Sarkoli and Ozewadi. The first report of white grub beetles from the Pandharpur Tahsil is provided in the present study. As a result, the inventory of the white grub beetles includes 15 species belonging to 9 genera and four subfamilies. Similar type of study on the white grub beetles from Arunachal Pradesh was carried out Chandra and Gupta (2012) and reported new distributional records of 12 species. Likewise many inventories have been carried out on the diversity, abundance and diet breadth of the white grub beetles from different geographic areas of the country (Chandra & Ahirwar, 2007; Chandra & Singh 2010; Chandra & Gupta, 2012).

The studies on white grub beetles with respect to their life cycle, population dynamics, diet breadth and their ecological requirements is still to be done from the Solapur

district, Maharashtra, especially from Pandharpur Tahsil. Nevertheless, based on the earlier published literature (Lefroy, 1971; Fletcher, 1914; Stebbing, 1914; Issac, 1919; Beeson, 1941; Brownie, 1968; Yadav and Mathur, 1987; Nair, 2007; Bhawane et al., 2012) species in the genera *Holotrichia*, *Maladera*, *Apogonia*, *Anomala*, *Adoretus*, *Chiloloba*, *Anatona*, *Oryctes* and *Phyllognathus* have been reported as pests of several agricultural crops, fruit trees, plantation crops and also in the forest nurseries. The faunal surveys in any area provide fundamental information which is essential for the conservation of the particular group or species and development of other management practices (Spector and Forsyth, 1998).

CONCLUSION

The present study is useful in future to assess the diversity, species richness, abundance of white grub beetles from the agro ecological zone of the Pandharpur Tahsil. The present information will also help in the management of pestiferous white grub beetles from Pandharpur Tahsil, District Solapur (M.S.) India.

TABLE 1: WHITE GRUB BEETLES (COLEOPTERA: SCARABAEIDAE) RECORDED FROM PANDHARPUR TAHSIL DURING MAY 2019 TO NOVEMBER 2015

Sr. No.	Name of species	Name of Subfamily
1	<i>Holotrichia fissa</i> Brenske	Melolonthinae
2	<i>Maladera castanea</i> Arrow	
3	<i>Maladera holosericea</i> Scopoli	
4	<i>Maladera</i> sp.	
5	<i>Apogonia</i> sp.	
6	<i>Anomala bengalensis</i> Blanchard	Rutelinae
7	<i>Anomala dorsalis</i> Fab.	
8	<i>Anomala</i> sp	
9	<i>Adoretus versutus</i> Harold	
10	<i>Adoretus</i> sp.	
11	<i>Adoretus</i> sp.	Cetoniinae
12	<i>Chiloloba acuta</i> Wied.	
13	<i>Anatona stillata</i> Newman	
14	<i>Oryctes rhinoceros</i> Linn.	
15	<i>Phyllognathus dionycious</i> Fab	Dynastinae

PLATE 1: WHITE GRUB BEETLES OF PANDHARPUR TAHSIL

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